

Zero Energy Building for DTU Building Design Bachelor

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Introduction

The new building for the new bachelor line of DTU Building Design is designed as a net zero energy building in the architectural context of the university. Besides energy consumption the project has a large focus on the Life Cycle Analysis of materials, indoor climate and total economy cost efficiency, while still aiming for high architectural standards in the experience of the facades, the area and internal flows and proportions.

The proposal can be seen as an opposition for the chosen new building 127 by Christensen og Co., which conceptual design has been made in the same period as the one for this project, but only compiling to the current building regulation. The project therefore shows the level of skills present at the department of Architectural Engineering and proposes a more ambitious strategy to the many new buildings needed at DTU in the coming years.